

Wind farms suitability location using geographical information system (GIS), based on multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methods: The case of continental Ecuador

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Abstract

The aim of this research was to implement a geographical information system with multi-criteria decision making methods, to select the most feasible location for installing wind power plants in continental Ecuador. In addition, a standardization process was performed, which consists of establishing an overall performance index to evaluate the results. Finally, the Pearson correlation coefficient is used to analyze mutual correspondence between multi-criteria decision making methods.

In this research, different selection criteria which include meteorological parameters (wind speed, air density), relief (slope), location (distances to substations, road network, urban areas, transmission lines, charging ports) and environmental parameters (vegetation coverage), have been considered.

The results of this research revealed that the site with the highest overall performance index is the Andean region of Ecuador, with an area of more than 617.5 km². The outcome of the overall performance index indicates that the four selected multi-criteria decision making methods provided similar results, where the value was equal to or greater than 75 % of the maximum punctuation of an ideal location. In this context, the methods analyzed converge to similar solutions and indicate that the multi-criteria decision making method is a powerful tool for selecting ideal locations for wind farms.

Keywords: location optimization, wind energy, wind farms, geographical information system (GIS), multi-criteria decision making (MCDM).

40 **1. Introduction**

41 Energy consumption is one of the clearest measures of progress and social welfare. In this
42 way, the function of the current economic model that depends on continuous expansion
43 requires an equal growth in the demand of energy is sustainable. However, an important
44 concept related to this issue is the "energy crisis", which occurs when the price in the supply
45 of energy resources rises within an economy. The energy crisis is currently of concern, due
46 to the world's demands on the limited natural resources that are used to power industrial
47 societies. These resources are diminishing as the overall demand rises. These natural
48 resources are available in limited supply as either they are finite, dependent on climatic
49 conditions or dependent on finite resources. Consequently fossil fuels are a finite resource,
50 which reveals the fact of the energy crisis in the world's economy. Additionally, the excessive
51 use of oil, gas and coal (or so called fossil fuels), produces more carbon dioxide (CO₂) than
52 the planet can maintain, which leads to global warming and ecological unsustainability. In
53 this regard, many countries worldwide introduce renewable energy systems in their energy
54 supply sources, to produce reliable and environmentally friendly energy.

55 A key feature of the expansion of renewable energies, on 2014 around the world was the
56 investment of \$131.3 BUS\$ in developing countries [1-2]. In the case of Ecuador, the
57 development of the energy sector has entered into a new phase since 2011 [3]. Ecuador is
58 rich in renewable energy resources such as wind, solar, geothermal and biomass. These
59 energy resources have not been explored in the past due to a solid fossil fuel energy supply.
60 Nowadays, Ecuador is transforming the energy mix in order to fulfill the country's energy
61 demand with renewable energy resources and environmentally sustainable standards. The
62 main changes in the energy mix are an increase in an optimal and sustainable manner of
63 access to primary energy resources, while changing residential and commercial consumption
64 patterns, as well as transportation possibilities, to more efficient ones. For this reason, 5227
65 MW of renewable energy power will be installed by 2022, which represents an investment
66 of 9.128 BUS\$, and will cover 83.61% of the country's energy demand [3]. In the case of
67 wind energy, Ecuador has explored the land's resources in the Andean, Coastal and Island
68 regions according to the Wind Atlas published by the Ministry of Electricity and Renewable
69 Energy of Ecuador (MEER) [4].

70 Wind power is considered the energy implantation source with the fastest growth in the world
71 [4, 5], according to five important factors listed below:

- 72 ● The need linked to the progressive depletion of fossil fuels and the search for
73 sustainable energy development without compromising future generations.
- 74 ● Potential for sufficient wind resources on various parts of the earth.
- 75 ● Technological capability to develop increasingly efficient wind turbines.
- 76 ● The vision of the pioneers in this field, who in the second half of the last century led
77 the technological development bringing us to the current situation.
- 78 ● The policies to facilitate the implementation of wind energy, both in terms of
79 administrative procedures and compensation for producers.

80 One of the inherent difficulties of wind power and renewable energy is the fitful nature of
81 production. A conventional energy source power plant can be located anywhere and does not

82 depend on where and how the fuel supply stands. Instead, wind farms must be located where
83 the wind is most available. In addition, the wind farm location is subjected to the wind
84 resources assessment, where the wind turbines on average work above 3 (m/s) wind speed
85 [4], [6]. Therefore, it is vital to choose the best location for wind farm settlement with
86 rigorous considerations, such as electrical and communication infrastructures and
87 environmental and economic feasibility.

88 This shortcoming can be dealt with by adopting a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM)
89 method. MCDM methods are important tools for the selection of wind farm locations,
90 because of their ability to provide adequate solutions. The evaluation of MCDM methods
91 compares different elements according to their characteristic properties in order to select the
92 best wind farm localization alternative (distance to urban areas, distance to distribution
93 substations and transmission lines, land uses, distance to ports, airports or terminals transport,
94 slope, wind speed, air density, etc.) [7-12].

95 The application of MCDM methods has been conducted in many disciplines. For instance,
96 Pohekar and Ramachandran [8] and Ho [10] performed an applications review, which
97 integrated the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). In addition, there are many examples of
98 the application of MCDM methods in renewable energy sources research, such as: Gwo-
99 Hsiung et al., [13], who studied the use of MCDM for new energy system development in
100 Taiwan by AHP and the Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Of
101 Evaluations (PROMETHEE). The decision makers (DSS) and PROMETHEE II for new
102 renewable energy exploitations have been applied by Georgopoulou et al., [14]. Pohekar and
103 Ramachandran [8] published a review for a sustainable energy-planning project, which
104 included MCDM methods such as PROMETHEE, AHP, Elimination and Choice Expressing
105 Reality (ELECTRE), Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
106 (TOPSIS), Fuzzy, etc. More recently, Amy et al., [15] developed a model based on AHP
107 associated with benefits, opportunities, costs and risks (BOCR), to perform a strategic
108 selection of wind farms in China. The VIKOR method to investigate the selection of a
109 renewable energy project in Spain has been applied by San Cristobal [16].

110 The MCDM methods in this research were processed with geographical information systems
111 (GIS). The use of GIS allows the organization, storage, manipulation, analysis and modeling
112 of large amounts of data from the real world that are linked to a spatial reference shaped grid.
113 GIS facilitates the incorporation of social, cultural, economic and environmental criteria that
114 leads to a more effective decision making. Furthermore, when GIS is joined to MCDM
115 methods, it provides a good tool for selecting the optimum site for wind farms. On the basis
116 of these conditions, the MCDM methods provide a range of techniques and procedures for
117 structuring the advantages, disadvantages and risks associated with the decision making
118 problem, evaluating the alternatives under specific considerations.

119 Several studies relating GIS-MCDM have been conducted about new energy resources such
120 as: Sanchez-Lozano et al., [17] who evaluated solar farm locations in south-eastern Spain
121 based on GIS and MCDM methods, as well as AHP and TOPSIS. GIS with an AHP-Ordered
122 Weighted Averaging (OWA) aggregation function to derive a wind farm land suitability
123 index, to spot wind farm locations in Oman has been developed by Al-Yahyai et al., [18].

124 Aydin et al., [19] applied GIS-based on the OWA method for wind farm locations in the west
125 of Turkey.

126 This research aimed to analyze the most feasible location for installing wind turbines based
127 on GIS-MCDM. The area of study was continental Ecuador, where no previous research has
128 been conducted. The MCDM methods applied to this research were the AHP method that
129 was implemented for calculating the weights, the (OWA) Occupational Repetitive Actions
130 (OCRA), VIKOR and TOPSIS. An Overall Performance Index (OPI) has been applied to
131 evaluate the results. Finally, the mutual correspondence between MCDM methods has been
132 evaluated by a Pearson correlation coefficient.

133 The current research is structured as following: The GIS is considered in section 2. The
134 methodology for the MCDM methods is described in section 3. The GIS-methodology
135 applied for the location of wind farms is exposed in section 4. The results are presented in
136 section 5. The discussion of the results is described in section 6. The conclusions of the
137 research are exposed in section 7.

138

139 **2. Material and methods**

140 **2.1 Geographic Information Systems**

141 GIS has been used as a tool of research and application since the 1970s. It involves a number
142 of academic fields including wind technology. GIS are designed to store, retrieve,
143 manipulate, analyze and map geographical data [20]. Raster and vector are the two types of
144 coverage representation with which GIS operates. The raster is represented by a rectangular
145 grid called pixels that contains specific information according to a specific geographic
146 location. Vectors maintain a geometric figure (points, lines and polygons), which define
147 limits that are associated with a reference system [17]. The storage of this information is
148 presented in a geodatabase which provides order, structure and standardization of the data.
149 All the geographic information was processed as a raster in this research, due to the
150 continuous analysis of the spatial variables such as: wind speed, terrain elevation, air density
151 and vegetation cover among others. GIS is a powerful tool in gathering and organizing spatial
152 data, as many successful examples to identify potential locations for generating renewable
153 energy emerge [20, 21].

154 The raster processes are faster in the evaluation of problems, including mathematical
155 combinations such as the MCDM methods. The MCDM in a GIS environment is based on
156 criteria represented by a layer of georeferenced cartographic information; therefore, every
157 point of the territory received a value regarding the object activity of the decision [21]. The
158 ArcGIS software was used to rasterize and standardize the data layers under linear and
159 logistic functions in this research. With this starting point and the inputs generated, the multi-
160 criteria analysis and the comparison of results were conducted using R, which is a
161 programming language specializing in calculus and statistics.

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163 **2.2. Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) methods**

164 Wind farm sitting is a MCDM problem. The selection is made by a number of alternative
165 locations in accordance with a set of criteria and possibilities. MCDM methods are analytical

166 tools employed to judge the best alternative of a set of possibilities and easy to adapt to
167 different requirements. The MCDM methods can be broadly divided into two categories; (i)
168 multi-objective decision making (MODM), and (ii) multi-attribute decision making
169 (MADM). There are also several methods in each of the above mentioned categories. Priority
170 based, outranking, preferential ranking, distance based and mixed methods, are some of the
171 popular MCDM methods commonly used to select a location for renewable energies [8, 10].
172 The AHP method has been widely applied in solving a variety of problems, including
173 applications related to planning renewable energy installations [13, 15, 18]. In this article the
174 AHP process has been used to calculate the weight of the criteria to install wind farms in
175 different locations. The OWA, OCRA, VIKOR and TOPSIS methods were used to evaluate
176 the problem. These methods were chosen because each alternative can be evaluated with the
177 GIS assessment criteria database. Finally, the Pearson correlation coefficient is used to
178 perform the statistical comparison between the different MCDM methods.

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180 **2.2.1 The Analytic hierarchy process (AHP) method**

181 The AHP is a structured technique to help people to deal with complex decisions. It was
182 developed by Thomas L. Saaty [9] in the 1970s and has been considerably improved since
183 then. The AHP identifies the important criteria for the decision making process. It creates a
184 hierarchical structure consisting of successive levels, starting from the overall objective,
185 sorting criteria and sub-criteria, and ending with the proposed alternatives.

186 The method employs a pair-wise comparison measurement mode to quantify the importance
187 of each criterion or sub-criterion, using a nine point internal scale.

188 A great amount of information about the AHP method is found in literature [8, 9, 22, 23].

189 The AHP method steps used in this research can be observed in figure 1.

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Figure 1. AHP method algorithm

194 **2.2.2 The Ordered Weighted Averaging (OWA) method**

195 The OWA method provides a parameterized family of aggregation operators, which have
196 been used in many applications [24]. An OWA operator of dimension n is a mapping $OWA: R^n$

197 $\rightarrow R$ that has an associated weighting vector W of dimension n having the properties $w_j \in [0, 1]$,
198 $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$ defined in equation (1).

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$$OWA(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \cdot b_j \quad (1)$$

201
202 Where b_j is the j th largest of the a_i .

203
204 **2.2.3 The Occupational Repetitive Actions (OCRA) method**

205 The OCRA method uses an intuitive technique to incorporate the preferences of the decision
206 maker on a relative importance of the criteria [11]. The OCRA method diagram can be
207 observed in figure 2.

208
209 Figure 2. OCRA method algorithm

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212 **2.2.4 The VIKOR method**

213 The VIKOR method was developed by Serafim Opricovic to solve decision problems with
214 different criteria [12]. VIKOR ranks alternatives and determines the solution, denominating
215 it as a “compromise”, obtaining the ideal solution. More information about the VIKOR

216 method is found in literature [12, 16]. The VIKOR method algorithm is presented in figure
217 3.

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219 Figure 3. VIKOR method algorithm.
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221 **2.2.5 The Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS)** 222 **method**

223 The TOPSIS method is a multiple criteria method to identify solutions from a finite set of
224 alternatives, developed by Hwang and Yoon [6]. The basic principle of the TOPSIS method
225 is to choose the alternative of the shortest and longest distance from the positive and negative
226 ideal solutions, respectively. An ideal solution is defined as a collection of scores or values
227 with the shortest geometric distance for all criterions considered. The TOPSIS method
228 diagram is presented in figure 4.
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Figure 4. TOPSIS method algorithm.

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2.2.6 Correlation between MCDM methods

234 Several techniques allow us to compare qualitatively and quantitatively raster maps,
235 recognizing visual or numerical similarities on the analyzed datasets at the current time [25].
236 Numerical comparisons use procedures based on statistical and mathematical modeling to
237 find relationships between large datasets [25].

238 As in other studies that are based on GIS techniques, in this research a pairwise comparison
239 of maps using the Pearson correlation is analyzed [26, 27]. The comparison has been
240 performed using the raster map values for processing each pixel at each method described in
241 MCDM methods.

242 In this research, the raster map solution of the MCDM methods was compared with the
243 Pearson correlation expressed in equation (2). In this context, each alternative was compared
244 twice, for all pixel values of each alternative and on the pixels which have a value greater
245 than 70. In the second case of comparison, six different masks were elaborated to compare
246 each method.

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$$\rho_{xy} = \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} \cdot \sqrt{n \sum y_i^2 - (\sum y_i)^2}} \quad (2)$$

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250 Where, x_i and y_i are the values of the raster maps to be compared, ρ_{xy} is the Pearson
251 Correlation Coefficient and n is the number of values analyzed.

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253 **2.3 GIS–MCDM methodology to prioritize locations for wind farms suitability**

254 Combining GIS with MCDM allows us to evaluate the criteria with its factors through the
255 use of attributes within a certain range of decision rules and assessment [17]. The most
256 common use of GIS-MCDM corresponds to the selection of suitable sites for locating human
257 activity.

258 For this assignment, a methodology based on the spatial analysis for the multi-criteria
259 evaluation was used. The research was performed in two stages; the first one was the
260 definition of factors and restrictions in the investigated area. Consequently, the information
261 was prepared by a rasterization and a standardization process. The second stage consisted in
262 an evaluation of the most suitable site through MCDM methods (figure 5). The AHP method
263 was used to quantify the importance of the different factors used during the process. Hence,
264 OWA, OCRA, VIKOR and TOPSIS were used to evaluate the different alternatives.

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Figure 5: Steps to develop the MCDM methods

268 **2.3.1 Definition of restrictions and factors.**

269 **2.3.1.1 Definition of the analyzed geographic extension**

270 The continental area of Ecuador has been selected for the implementation of wind farms in
271 this research (figure 6). The area covers 249 000 km², which includes all the continental
272 provinces of Ecuador.

273 MEER published the Wind Atlas of Ecuador in 2013 [4]. The wind resource modeling is
274 operated with a spatial resolution of 200 m x 200 m and the integration of a digital map that
275 uses geoprocessing resources, which calculate the performance and electrical energy
276 production. All the information considered in this research was presented in the raster format,
277 with the same resolution and extension as the Wind Atlas of Ecuador [4].
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279
280 Figure 6: Continental Ecuador separated by regions and provinces.
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282 **2.3.1.2 Compilation of cartographic information and identification of factors and**
283 **restrictions**

284 The raster and vector cartographic information was determined with help from Ecuadorian
285 government's public institutions as it is presented in table 1. The information includes
286 different criteria such as physical, socio-economic, technical and environmental issues. In
287 order to perform the evaluation of land suitability, the following criteria were considered:
288 wind speed, digital elevation model, distance of substations, air density, distance to roads,

289 distance to transmission lines, vegetation coverage and land use, charging ports distance,
 290 urban areas, etc. Criteria were considered as factors or restrictions within the MCDM
 291 methods.

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Table 1: Cartographic information and identification of factors and restrictions

Criterion	Institution	Year	Identification of factors and restrictions
Wind speed over 80 m above ground level (agl)	Ministry of electricity and renewable energy	2013	Factor
Digital elevation model	Ministry of electricity and renewable energy	2013	Factor
Substations distance	Agency of regulation and control of electricity	2015	Factor
Air density	National institute for energy efficiency and renewable energy	2015	Factor
Road network	Ministry of transport and public works	2015	Factor
Transmission lines	Agency of regulation and control of electricity	2015	Factor
Vegetation coverage and land use	Ministry of agriculture, aquaculture and fishing	2002	Factor
Charging ports	Ministry of transport and public works	2012	Factor
Urban area	Military geographical institute	2013	Factor / Restriction
Flood area	National institute of meteorology and Hydrology - ministry of agriculture, aquaculture and fishing	2002	Restriction
Volcanic hazard	Risk management secretariat	2009	Restriction
Airports	Ministry of transport and public works	2012	Restriction
National system of protected areas	Ministry of environment	2015	Restriction
Mangroves	Ministry of environment	2015	Restriction
Archeology	National institute for cultural heritage	2015	Restriction

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295 The restrictions reduce the positive wind farm suitability over the studied area, based on
 296 policy or social-environmental issues. In most cases, legal restrictions were taken into
 297 account to establish the suitable areas to locate wind farms. While in other cases, the physical
 298 impossibility or simply the inadequacy of the land was a sufficient restrictive criterion to
 299 eliminate certain areas. However, most of the restrictions are due to legislation, so an
 300 inventory of the legal framework had to be established with the current laws [28, 29].

301 Environmental impacts associated with wind farm energy generation are commonly accepted
 302 and considered by scientists. These impacts are generally listed as effects on animal habitats
 303 such as bird collisions, noise generation, visual impact, safety issues, electromagnetic
 304 interference, and distance to airports and to population centers. Moreover, flood area,
 305 seismicity and volcanic hazards are considered as a restriction because these natural

306 phenomena can cause structural damage to wind farms or even electric shock [15, 18, 19, 30,
 307 31].
 308 The identified criteria of restrictions based on literature reviews is presented in table 2, and
 309 the map of suitable and restricted areas for wind farm site location is illustrated in figure 7.
 310 The layer of the Ecuadorian territory with all the land register includes 6 225 000 pixels, each
 311 of which is a record in the database that has the following assigned information: A filter was
 312 performed on the layer with the restricted areas. The raster included 3 832 583 pixels located
 313 in suitable areas.
 314

315 Table 2: Criteria of restrictions

Criteria	Restriction
Urban area	Considered 3000 m of security area [32]
Flood area	Completely restricted area
Volcanic hazard	Completely restricted area
Airports	Completely restricted area or 2500 m away from airports [32]
National system of protected areas	Completely restricted area or 250 m from ecologically sensitive areas [33]
Mangroves	Completely restricted area or 4000 m from water bodies [34]
Archeology	Completely restricted area

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Figure 7: Map of suitable and restricted areas for wind farm site selection.

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Factors are based on the weighting and compensation variables that will influence positively (aptitude) or negatively (impact) on the activity of the object of decision, so they should be inventoried and classified previously [22]. Table 1 presents the summary of layers with information selected as factors for this study, which have been selected by its positive and negative importance and influence the analysis in this manner. The coverage criteria considered in the analysis of the study was wind speed, ground slope, distance to the electrical substations and to the road, transmission lines, distribution lines and seaports, which are described in more detail below:

- The wind speed model selected was the 80 m above ground level (agl), according to the wind turbines mean hub height for 2 MW of nominal capacity at 11-13 m/s. The

330 wind speed was integrated in the Ecuadorian surface. In this case, the annual average
331 wind speed was equal to or higher than 7 m/s [4].

332 • For the elevation digital model, the average ground slope criteria established as not
333 exceeding 15%. For this reason, the most suitable areas were those that had zero
334 slopes, and the least suitable sites were those with average ground slopes of maximum
335 15% [4].

336 • The construction of wind farms close to existing electric substations, road network,
337 to the transmission and distribution lines, is preferable [17, 18, 22]. The construction
338 of this infrastructure causes deforestation, disruption of habitats and wildlife crossing,
339 urban sprawl and an increased cost and transport of construction materials over long
340 distances, which also increases the emitted pollutants [22]. Distances to the electric
341 substations, to the road network, to the transmission and to the distribution lines can
342 be minimized by different methods such as Euclidean distance, Euclidean Allocation,
343 Euclidean direction, cost distance, etc. In this research the Euclidean distance to the
344 suggested wind farms site has been used. These conditions could reduce costs in the
345 implementation phase and amortize the investment in a short time period. In this
346 manner, costs for machinery and equipment transportation; as well as increasing the
347 electrical grid would be less expensive. Several examples can be consulted in the
348 literature for how to employ this tool to reduce distances [18, 19, 22].

349 • The seaports are the most important transport terminals, where different equipment
350 and machinery for the wind farm project enters the country. The different charging
351 ports selected influence in the costs of the project, according to the distances to the
352 ports. Therefore, the costs will be lower if the charging ports located in the coastline
353 are closer to the wind farms. Due to the aforementioned reasons, the Euclidean
354 distance has been taken into account to minimize the distance to seaports.

355 • According to the bibliography [4], the turbine power density depends on the air
356 density. In the case of high altitudes as in the Andean region, there is low air density
357 and high wind speed, which comprehends areas of great interest for further
358 investigation [4].

359 • The optimal areas considered for the construction of a wind farm are those that
360 present no vegetation coverage and a high degree of alteration by human intervention.
361 It is not possible to build wind farms in urban areas because they affect the residents'
362 wellbeing. Therefore, a 3000 m security zone from urban areas was considered as a
363 forbidden location to generate wind power [19].

364

365 **2.3.2 Preparation of information**

366 Preparing information is related to the organization and layout of geographic information for
367 its analysis with different MCDM solution methods. During this period, original data was
368 transformed in different procedures to secure its appropriate use during the MCDM
369 evaluation.

370 **2.3.2.1 Rasterization**

371 The analyzed data employed in this study was available as vector structures (point, lines or
 372 polygons), or as a matrix structure, called raster. To convert vector coverage to a raster format
 373 requires an acquainted extension grid. The precision of the extension grid is defined by the
 374 cells size. In this case, the pixel size was 200 m x 200 m, and the extension grid covered the
 375 continental territory of Ecuador. The MCDM requires a raster where each pixel contains a
 376 numerical attribute according to the represented variable. Therefore, rasterization is
 377 considered a previous assignment in order to continue with the MCDM methods.

378 In the rasterization process, each type of variable to be transformed is considered. A raster
 379 model derived from original information is considered as a factor model. Moreover, vector
 380 structures are simply transformed to raster like structures when dealing with a restriction.
 381 Rasterization processes of applied values in different coverages are summarized in table 3.

382

383 Table 3: Rasterization processes applied to each criteria of information

Criteria	Rasterization
Wind speed over 80 m agl	No transformation
Digital elevation model	Calculating slopes
Substations	Euclidean distance calculation
Air density	Air density map is estimated from ISO 2533-1975.
Road network	Euclidean distance calculation
Transmission lines	Euclidean distance calculation
Vegetation coverage and land use	Value assignment and rasterization
Charging ports	Euclidean distance calculation
Urban area	Euclidean distance calculation
Urban area	Transformation binary raster
Flood area	Transformation binary raster
Volcanic hazard	Transformation binary raster
Airports	Transformation binary raster
National system of protected areas	Transformation binary raster
Mangroves	Transformation binary raster
Archeology	Transformation binary raster

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385 The air density map was estimated from the ideal gas relation based on ISO 2533-1975,
 386 which depends on atmospheric pressure and temperature. The temperature map was
 387 calculated with weather values/data from the National Institute of Meteorology and
 388 Hydrology of Ecuador (INAMHI), that were interpolated using regionalization
 389 methodologies of meteorological variables of Fries et al. and the National Institute of Energy
 390 Efficiency and Renewable Energy of Ecuador (INER) [35, 36].The raster map is based on
 391 data with normal climate from 1981 to 2010 and maintains the previous analyzed resolution.
 392 The atmospheric pressure map was estimated through the barometric relation between
 393 altitude and pressure, which was obtained from the hydrostatic equation [37, 38]. This
 394 relation is expressed in equation (3).

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$$p(h, T) = P_0 e^{-\frac{mgh}{kT}} \quad (3)$$

Where, $p(h, T)$ is the atmospheric pressure at a height above sea level, P_0 is the atmospheric pressure at sea level, which is approximated 1010 hPa, g is gravity, and k is the Boltzmann constant. Last, h and T correspond to the elevation and temperature map. The constant m is estimated from the molar mass M_A of air and the Avogadro number, N_A where $m = M_A \cdot N_A$. Air density is estimated from the relation of ideal gases, as the standard ISO 2533:1975 [39] recommends. Air density is expressed in equation (4).

$$\rho_a(T, p(h, T)) = \frac{M_a p(h, T)}{RT} \quad (4)$$

Where, ρ_a is the air density, M_a is the air molar mass equal to 0.02896 kg/mol, R is the universal gas constant equal to 8.314 Pa*m³/mol*K. Replacing equation (3) in equation (4) the air density regarding altitude and temperature is obtained in equation (5).

$$\rho_a(T, p(h, T)) = \frac{M_a P_0 e^{-\frac{mgh}{kT}}}{RT} \quad (5)$$

2.3.2.2 Factors standardization

For the selection of wind power plants it is necessary to consider factors such as wind speed, distance to electrical substations, air density etc., which do not have linear behavior in the standardization process for the site selection. The optimal values of these factors must be prioritized in each case, so most of the time a linear function should not be used.

The standardization process consists of a rescale of raster values that starts using a mathematical function (line or curve), specified according to predefined standardization criteria.

In a suitability model, the decreasing logistic function is ideal when the minor incoming values are less preferred. When the incoming values increase, the preference decreases rapidly to a stage where the minimal preferences are established for higher incoming values. While the preferences in transformation logistic functions increase instead of decreasing [40]. Meanwhile, the transformation of the linear function is ideal when the preferences for the values increase or decrease linearly [40].

The resulting scale is a range of continuous whole values between 1 and 100, where the minor value is the less important and the highest value is the most representative. In this assignment logistic or linear functions were used according to the variable, as illustrated in table 4.

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Table 4: Functions applied for factor standardization

Id	Factor	Standardize function
a	Wind speed	Logistic growth
b	Slope	Decreasing function
c	Distance to electrical substations	Logistic growth
d	Air density	Logistic growth
e	Distance to road network	Logistic growth
f	Distance to an urban area	Logistic growth
g	Distance to transmission lines	Logistic growth
h	Vegetation coverage and land use	Value Assignment
i	Distance to charging ports	Linear function and cost distance

432

433 The resulting layers of the factor standardization process mentioned in table 4 are illustrated
434 in figure 8. All layers that were considered as factors present values between 1 and 100 for
435 this calculation. However, layers considered as restrictions were added in just one binary
436 layer map that represents values of 0 (Restricted) and 1 (Unrestricted), as illustrated in figure
437 7.

438
439

Figure 8: Layers of the factor standardization

440 **2.3.3 MCDM evaluation**

441 Once the factors have been standardized it is necessary to calculate the weight of the specific
442 criteria, to put the problem under analysis.

443 Wind power plants can be considered desirable. However, they produce adverse effects on
444 society or on the environment. Although a wind farm may cover a large area of land, other
445 land uses like agriculture are compatible with it. The location of new wind farms can upgrade
446 the electrical grid and infrastructure needed for its operation.

447 Four elements were determined by their importance for this research: meteorological, relief,
448 location and environmental. The factors were classified according to its correspondence and
449 importance within the different categories. Figure 9 presents the hierarchy of criteria subject
450 to serve as a starting point for the application of the AHP.

451

452

453

454

Figure 9: Hierarchy of criteria and factors.

455 The criteria weights that influenced the decision problem were obtained from literature [15,
456 17-19], in order to choose the most suitable site for installing wind farms. The obtained
457 results of the application of the AHP method are presented in table 5. Therefore, the most
458 important element was the meteorological (53.1%), the second one was the relief (21.5%),
459 the third one the location (21.5%), and the least important was the environmental (3.9%).

Table 5: Component weights and its factors

Category	Weight	Factor	Weight
Meteorological	0.5309	Wind speed	0.3982
		Air density	0.1327
Relief	0.2151	Slope	0.2151
Location	0.2150	Distance to electrical substations	0.1009
		Distance to road network	0.0432
		Distance to urban area	0.0432
		Distance to transmission lines	0.0185
		Distance to charging ports	0.0092
Environmental	0.0390	Vegetation coverage and land use	0.0390

461

462 3. Results

463 Nine factors employed in this study were the inputs to the OWA, OCRA, VIKOR and
 464 TOPSIS methods, to find the most suitable location for installing wind farms in Ecuador. The
 465 results have been obtained based on the relative weights calculated with the AHP method,
 466 which are illustrated in table 5. In addition, an OPI to evaluate the results from 1 to 100 was
 467 accomplished. The evaluation of the score from 1 to 100 clarifies that the score is
 468 proportional to the degree of suitability of the land. A high score indicates that the analyzed
 469 area is a suitable site for a wind farm. This assignment allows for choosing category ranges
 470 with more flexibility and precision, in a way that the best results are obtained with the least
 471 possible risks. The above mentioned OPI is divided into three intervals, so that each interval
 472 indicates a different capacity that contains suitable pixels; the marginally (1-49), the
 473 moderate (50-74) and the most (75-100).

474 The distribution of the most suitable land and the restricted areas is presented in figure 10.
 475 Hence, the suitable land for the installation of wind farms was 61.9 %. Therefore the usable
 476 area was about 154380 km². With the prior determined factors and application of MCDM,
 477 an assessment classification was obtained that demonstrated that the most suitable locations
 478 to install wind farms were below 0.4%, which represents up to 617.5 km². Meanwhile the
 479 moderately suitable area was between 1.1% and 29.7%, and lastly, the marginally suitable
 480 surface was between 69.8% and 98.5%.

481

482 Figure 10: Suitability surface distribution (left) and MCDM methods classification for
 483 suitable land surface (right).
 484

485 The ranking of the land suitability index map in the study area for OWA, OCRA, VIKOR
 486 and TOPSIS methods is illustrated in figure 11. The case study results show the most
 487 appropriate locations in red. These sites were settled in the Andean region, specifically in the
 488 provinces of Pichincha, Cotopaxi, Bolívar, Chimborazo, Azuay and Loja (figure 6). The sites
 489 with scores below the threshold of 70 have been found on the western area of the country
 490 (figure 11), which correspond to the Pacific Ocean coastline. This region presented good
 491 results at OWA, VIKOR and OCRA methods, but, generally revealed a score below 45 for
 492 the TOPSIS method. Finally, the region with the lowest obtained scores after the MCDM
 493 analysis corresponded to the eastern part of Ecuador, the Amazon region.

494
 495 Figure 11: Ranking of the land suitability index map in the study area for OWA, OCRA,
 496 VIKOR and TOPSIS methods
 497

498 **4. Discussion**

499 The increasing population and improving living standards produce an increment on the
 500 energy demand. At this point, the future of the world's oil supply is uncertain. Over the last
 501 few years, a major concern has arisen regarding the decrease of the global oil reserves,
 502 through the increment of fuel demand in emerging economies and the associated instability
 503 of the crude oil price, driven by a strong international demand and by political instabilities
 504 within the oil producing regions. In addition, fossil fuels consumption has a negative impact

505 on the environment. To solve this issue, the production of reliable and sustainable energy
506 from renewable sources is proposed. In this context, wind power plants could solve the
507 problem of energy demand in some places.
508 This research developed and applied GIS with four MCDM methods and the Pearson
509 correlation coefficient to assess the suitability of building wind farms in the continental area
510 of Ecuador. The study contributes with new added credibility of the use of expert validation
511 the existing literature about GIS-based renewable energy suitability studies. This is the first
512 Ecuadorian research to specifically evaluate the most suitable wind farms using GIS-MCDM.
513 The results support future decision making to the government of Ecuador, when building
514 more renewable energy infrastructures based on wind power plants in relation with the energy
515 mix change.
516 To contrast the results with the different MCDM methods, an analysis of the results by a
517 Pearson correlation coefficient has been performed. The results of the Pearson correlation
518 coefficient for each MCDM method are presented in Figure 12. It can be noticed that for the
519 OWA, VIKOR and OCRA method, the correlation of the results is above 93%. While in the
520 case of the TOPSIS method, the correlation of the results is about 53%. This is due to the
521 value difference in the western of Ecuador between TOPSIS and the other methods.

522

523 Figure 12: Results of the Pearson coefficient correlation between MCDM methods for all
 524 values.

525

526 The results of the Pearson correlation coefficient for each MCDM method taking a data
 527 threshold value above 70 are illustrated in Figure 13. Besides this, with OWA, VIKOR and
 528 OCRA methods, the correlation of the results is maintained above 93%, while in the case of
 529 the correlation method TOPSIS, a value equal or greater than 75% was achieved. These
 530 results indicate that the four MCDM present similar outcomes in a value equal to or greater
 531 than 75% for the best places to install a wind farm.

532
 533 Figure 13: Results of Pearson correlation coefficient for each MCDM. It has been taken a
 534 data threshold value above 70.
 535

536 The overriding consensus in bibliography is a minimal environmental impact caused by wind
 537 farms compared with other forms of power generation [19, 41]. This opinion was supported
 538 by the different selection criteria considered by the experts as Al-Yahyai et al., [18], including
 539 economical (distance to road, terrain slope), social (urban area), environmental (historical
 540 locations, wildlife and natural reserves) and technical (wind power density, energy demand
 541 matching, percentage of sustainable wind, turbulence intensity, sand dunes) factors. In case
 542 of Van Haren and Fthenakis, [42] the considered criteria were economic (wind resources,
 543 electric line cost, electric integration cost, land cost, access road cost), planning (visual
 544 impact, safety distances urban areas, electromagnetic interference, parks, military, airports,
 545 prisons, etc.) and physical (slope, altitude, karst ecological bird habitats/routes, forest

546 proximity, lakes and rivers). Similar criteria and restrictions were also taken by Aydin in [19]
547 and also Watson and Hutson [43]. In this case, the selection criteria included meteorological
548 (wind speed, air density), relief (slope), location (distances to substations, road network,
549 urban area, transmission lines, charging ports) and environmental (vegetation coverages)
550 parameters, which are in relation with the literature mentioned before.

551 The MCDM used to evaluate the capacity to fit different locations to install wind farms in
552 the research of Al-Yahyai et al [18] were AHP-OWA aggregation. Aydin [19] used the OWA
553 method. Meanwhile, Watson and Hutson [43] used the AHP and pairwise comparison. In this
554 study, the AHP method has been used for calculating the weights and the OWA, OCRA,
555 VIKOR and TOPSIS methods were used to rank the alternatives. Moreover, the correlation
556 coefficient was used to analyze mutual correspondence between the MCDM methods. The
557 use of a larger number of MCDM methods and the correlation coefficient provided greater
558 consistency to the results.

559 The outcome related with the research conducted by Van Haren and Fthenakis [42], Aydin
560 in [19] and Watson and Hutson [43], exposed areas that were suitable for installing wind
561 farms, although the results were not representative for the entire country. Furthermore, it did
562 not present the total percentages of suitable land for locating the wind farms. In the case of
563 Al-Yahyai et al., [18], the case study results demonstrated that the area with the most suitable
564 classification represented about 0.2% of the total area of Oman. However, in the case of
565 Ecuador the suitable locations for installing wind farms are above 0.4%. The variation in the
566 outcome between the two studies is due to the weight of the criteria. In the case study of Al-
567 Yahyai et al [18] wind occurrence is the most important criteria, while in the case of Ecuador
568 there are large variations in the occurrence of wind.

569

570 **5. Conclusions**

571 In this research, the selection of places for installing wind power plants has been achieved
572 based on GIS-MCDM methods for Ecuador. The present study found that due to the
573 environmental characteristics of the climate, terrain, location and despite all the restrictive
574 criteria or limitations, the valid target area has a high rate of acceptance for the
575 implementation of wind farms.

576 In order to evaluate the location of wind farms in Ecuador, the VIKOR, OCRA, TOPSIS and
577 OWA methods were applied. The results show that the most appropriate land overall is in the
578 Andean region of Ecuador. This surface represents between 0.4% and 1.1% of the total area
579 of Ecuador. The areas with the lowest scores are located at the east of the country.

580 Two statistical comparisons with the Pearson correlation coefficient have been performed
581 using arrays of pairs between methods. In the first comparison all raster values were used,
582 while in the second comparison the highest pixel values (>70), of each pair were selected as
583 raster. It has been observed that there is a correlation of 75% between MCDM methods for
584 selecting the most suitable location to install a wind farm.

585 To conclude, this study demonstrates that the use of GIS-MCDM tools facilitate the selection
586 of the most feasible location in the field of renewable energy sources. These techniques will
587 help researchers in the future to find locations from an energy development perspective.

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596

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